

Ideal Gas Law, Sackur-Tetrode Formula and First Law of Thermodynamics for a Deterministic System?

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Statistical mechanics presumably deals with probabilities and statistics, i.e. uncertainties. In practice, such uncertainty appears in an ideal gas through two body collisions which change the energy and velocity of the particle, its direction etc. One does not have all of the information linked to a collision and so conservation of energy is applied leaving a fair amount of uncertainty and forcing the system to be described in a probabilistic manner.

Here, we wish to consider a very simple deterministic, single particle system and show that it may be described by the ideal gas law, the Sackur-Tetrode formula and the first law of thermodynamics. This leads to the question: How can a deterministic system with a single particle with a constant, known speed, be described in terms of thermodynamics?

We suggest that the notion of pressure is one which requires the use of an average. Physically, a single particle with a constant speed strikes a wall and reflects elastically at some time and then, until it returns, no force is exerted on the wall. Pressure, on the other hand, exists at all times and so may be seen as an average over time. This means that one obscures time details between successive hits, i.e. uses units of cycle time which bypass times associated with motion $x=vt$. For example, if one has a 1-D container of size L and another, of size $2L$, each containing a particle with speed v , then using the statistical formula for pressure: $N/L v p$, one finds that the $2L$ box has half the pressure. This means that in a cycle time $t = 2L/v$, there is one hit against the wall in the $2L$ box and two in the L box, making the average force/pressure double in the L box. Given that one is considering averaging over time cycles, the explicit idea is that one is not following a particle in time. We have already shown in a previous note (1) that this means that there is a position probability of $1/V$ ($1/L$). In other words, averaging over time cycles, even in a deterministic system, seems to give rise to thermodynamics. We try to show that not only does the ideal gas law hold for a particle with a constant speed in a box of size L , but also the first law of thermodynamics. In addition, the 1-D Sackur-Tetrode equation also appears. Thus, equations which are seemingly to be applied to a stochastic system with fluctuations actually also seem to apply to a deterministic system if one obscures some information, namely time and uses a kind of coarse graining of the variable to cycle times.

Usual Statistical Aspects of an Ideal Gas

An ideal gas is composed of N particles with a total energy of E . In Newtonian mechanics, if one knows all parameters involved in a collision, one could presumably predict the outcome of such a collision. In other words, there would be no uncertainty or probability and hence no statistical mechanics. If one decides to ignore a large amount of relevant collision information and only impose a conservation of energy constraint with energy as the sole piece of information (together with momentum), then collisions become probabilistic with e_1+e_2 becoming e_3+e_4 and probabilities $p(e_i)$ existing. By assuming that $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$ unnormalized and $e_1+e_2 = (e_1+e_2)$, one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, $C \exp(-e_i/T)$. In other words, the system seems to be clearly stochastic. We suggest, however,

that this is due to the removal of information linked to collisions (except e, p and their conservations) and also a lack of following a particle in time. This second assumption leads to the notion of pressure as a value which exists for all times even though the force on the wall is granular and due to specific particle hits. If $N \rightarrow \infty$, however, which is the assumption used for an ideal gas, then pressure does seem to hold at each instant and have the same value to a very good approximation, it seems.

As a result, one has several key results for an ideal gas:

$$E = \frac{3}{2} NRT \text{ (3 dimensions) or } E = \frac{1}{2} NRT \text{ (1 dimension) ((1a))}$$

$$PV = nRT \text{ ((1b)) and } dE = TdS - PdV \text{ ((1c))}$$

and S proportional to $\ln(V) T^{\text{power } 3/2}$ (3 dimensions) ((1d)) (for one dimension, one would have power $1/2$).

The question we ask here is: Can ((1a)) -((1d)) be applied to a simple, obviously deterministic system? The specific system we consider is a single particle with a constant speed v in a box of length L . We argue that one may apply ((1a)) -((1d)) even though there seems to be no stochasticity or fluctuations whatsoever in this box system. We suggest that ((1a)) -((1d)) apply through the removal of information. In other words, it is the removal of information which leads to stochasticity, we argue.

Deterministic Single Particle with Constant Speed in a 1-D box of Size L

We consider a single particle with constant speed v in a 1-D box of size L which bounces elastically off of the walls. This is a deterministic Newtonian situation, but only if one measures time. In such a case, one has:

$$x = vt \text{ if } x=0, t=0 \text{ ((2))}$$

The point we make is that if one does not measure time, then even if the system is completely deterministic (not in any way stochastic), the loss of time information leads to uncertainty and probability. In particular, with no time or initial conditions, the particle has equal probability to be at any point in the box, hence:

$$p(x) = 1/L \text{ ((3))}$$

In (1), we explicitly showed that if a particle is at a point x in a box, this point may be mapped to a set of possible times. If one applies these same times to a particle in a box of size $2L$ (same speed and initial conditions), then the particle may be at two distinct spatial points. A box of size $3L$ leads to three distinct spatial points etc. Thus, there is probability through information removal, not inherent fluctuations etc.

Ideal Gas Law

We next suggest introducing the concept of pressure for the single particle, but this requires averaging over cycle times. Physically, a single particle hits a wall and bounces back, imparting a force, but then for a cycle time there is no further force. Pressure is supposed to exist for all times and so, it seems, it must be considered to be an average. Thus, one imposes the notion of an average (statistical concept) on a purely deterministic system. This means that one does not follow the particle in time during a cycle meaning that it could be anywhere in L with equal probability. We use the usual textbook formula for a pressure, but apply it now to the deterministic single particle scenario:

$$\text{Pressure} = N/L v p \quad ((4)) \quad N=1$$

$$\text{Now: } E=KE = .5 m v^2 \text{ so for 1-D: } P L = T \quad ((5)) \text{ where } E=.5 T \quad ((6))$$

((5)) is the ideal gas law applied to the completely deterministic system.

First Law of Thermodynamics

If one examines the ideal gas law ((5)) for the single particle deterministic system, then:

$$(dP) L + P dL = dT \quad ((7))$$

((7)) already suggests a kind of first law form, but dP is unknown. We next consider the basic Newtonian idea that a single particle in a box may receive energy in two ways. First, one may give it energy directly inside the box by sending it a "photon" which strikes it inside. Secondly, one may move the box wall very slowly so that dL is achieved over a time cycle. This approach changes both L and imparts extra energy to the particle.

We have argued that given that one uses time cycles as a time unit, there are no time details within a cycle. This means that one does not know where the particle is and one does not really know when the kinetic energy changes. One only has large time units such that the wall has changed from one large time unit to another, but microscopically, the actual collision of the single particle with the wall could have occurred at various different unknown times.

The two manners of imparting energy to the deterministic particle follow directly from Newtonian mechanics, although the pressure related work requires an average over time. It seems that the first law of thermodynamics follows directly from these two ways of imparting energy.

$$\text{First, one may have only the an internal energy change, i.e. } v \rightarrow v+dv \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Then: } dE = d(\text{nonwork function of } T,L) \quad ((9))$$

On the other hand, if the wall is moved slowly, this is Newtonian work and one should have:

$$dE = -PdL \quad ((10))$$

In such a case, T (meaning mv^2) and L change so d (no work function) must be 0, but nonzero for only a change in T with L fixed. This suggests mathematically that d (work function) be composed to two terms, one which matches dE (as a function of $T=mv^2$) and the other balancing $-PdL$. In the case of both T and L changing, the two terms of d (no work function) cancel each other.

We first consider L constant and $v \rightarrow v+dv$ as an infinitesimal.

$$dE = d(.5 T) = .5 dT \quad \text{where } T = mv^2 \quad ((11))$$

This suggests a possible term of: $T d \ln(T \text{ power } .5)$. We try to use \ln because it is known that the spatial probability is $1/L$ and $d \ln(1/L) = -dL/L$ which matches the ideal gas law:

$$P L = T \rightarrow -PdL = -T dL/L \quad ((12))$$

For $dE = -P dL$ one has dL as negative and: $.5 dT = T/L |dL|$

Thus we replace d (no work function) with $T d$ (no work function) :

$$T d(\text{no work function}) = T \{ \ln(L) + \ln(T \text{ power } .5) \} \quad ((13))$$

((13)) is essentially the Sackur-Tetrode equation in 1-D.

In other words $T d$ (no work function) mimics both dE and $-P dL$. This $T d$ (no work function), however, is:

$$TdS \quad \text{in the first law of thermodynamics} \quad ((14))$$

Thus, one may have entropy due to a lack of time knowledge and time averaging even in a completely deterministic system. This, we suggest, leads to the ideal gas law equations ((4)), ((5)) and ((6)) as well as to the first law of thermodynamics describing such a system even though it is not stochastic at all and has no fluctuations. In addition, one has the Sackur-Tetrode equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present a simple deterministic example of a single particle moving at constant speed in a 1-D box of length L and bouncing elastically off the walls. We suggest that if one introduces the idea of pressure, this concept involves a time average over time units on the length of a cycle time. This suggests that one coarse grains and does not pay attention to times smaller than this. In other words, one does not follow the particle as $x=vt$ (initial conditions $x=0$, $t=0$). In such a case, the particle has spatial entropy as it may be anywhere in L with equal

probability. We suggest that the ideal gas law $P L = T$ applies if $T=mvv$. This follows from the usual definition of pressure in an ideal gas, but here, T is not linked to any average of kinetic energies as there are no stochastic collisions or fluctuations. We then have: $E = .5 T$ in one dimension.

From purely Newtonian considerations (together with the time average of P), one may suggest that the particle may receive energy internally so that $v \rightarrow v+dv$ with L remaining fixed, or one may move the wall slowly (over a cycle time) so that both v and L change. In the first case: $dE = .5 dT = d$ (no work function), meaning that there exists a function of T and L which is not the usual Newtonian $-PdL$ function. This is how entropy appears in this deterministic problem with time removed up to cycle time units. In the case of the wall being pushed: $dE = -P dL$ ($dL < 0$) and so the d (no work function) must cancel meaning that dT and dL proportional terms cancel. This suggests that they mimic dE and $-P dL$ and leads to the Sackur-Tetrode equation as well as the first law of thermodynamics for a completely deterministic example of a single particle with constant v in a box of length L , we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Volume Information Entropy and Classical Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2025)